

Predicting The Structure of Anopheles Gambiae, Cytochrome P450 Protein In-Silico

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Abstract

The CYP12F4 protein is a member of the Cytochrome P450 super-family of monooxygenases, a large and diverse group of enzymes that catalyzes the oxidation of organic substances and metabolic reactions. It is found in the female African Mosquito *Anopheles gambiae* (*A. gambiae*) that carries and transmits the most deadly malaria parasite, *Plasmodium falciparum* (Pf). It has been found to be overtranscribed in the resistant phenotype (KWAG-perm) and steroidogenic ovaries/ steroidogenic MRTs compared to non-steroidogenic ovaries. Experimental structure is not available for this protein; it has thus remained uncharacterized with unknown functions.

This work employs in-silico methods to predict the structure of this metabolic catalyzer and further deduced a specific function for the same protein. Using 6 template proteins of 39 of residues modeled at >90% confidence based on ab initio method, Phyre2 web server was deployed to predict a computational model for CYP12F4. GOPET web tool was finally used to deduce the unique function of this protein. The folds were identified and analyzed and the protein was specifically found to be active in binding of molecules with 86% confidence value with various catalysis activities. 20 helices, 16 strands, 48 turn and 348 hydrogen bonds were elucidated and analyzed on the structure.

Several literatures have confirmed these findings. CYP12F4 is a heme and iron ion binding protein that carries heme and catalyses the incorporation of one atom from molecular oxygen into a compound and reduces the other atom of oxygen to water. A deep understanding of these properties of heme and its binding with respect to CYP12F4 protein is vital in drug design for malaria.

Keywords —*Anopheles gambiae*, In-silico, structure prediction, P450